

- *BRCA1*: c.80+5G>A (exon 2) weakens the natural donor (R_i [the information content of the splice site]) from 8.9 -> 5.8 bits, which decreases the overall strength of the exon ($R_{i,total}$ [total information of the exon] = 11.1 -> 8.0 bits), and may lead to an increase to exon 2 skipping [experimental result described by authors: skipping was observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.134+5G>T (exon 3) significantly weakens the natural donor ($R_i = 8.3$ -> 5.0 bits; $R_{i,total} = 10.9$ -> 7.6 bits) and could result in exon skipping, but may also activate a pre-existing cryptic site ($R_i = 5.0$ bits) 103nt upstream [however, only exon skipping isoform was observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.1878A>G (exon 10) strengthens a 4.1 bit cryptic donor site, resulting in an 1208nt long exon ($R_{i,total}$: 1.6 -> 4.6 bits; ~ 8 fold), which is the fourth ranked isoform of the region, and thus is not expected to be the dominant splice form [alternate mRNA splicing was not observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.4115G>A (exon 11) slightly increases strength of a pre-existing cryptic donor ($R_i = 2.8$ -> 3.6 bits; $R_{i,total} = 5.4$ bits), which is much weaker than natural exon 11 ($R_{i,total} = 15.0$ bits) and is not expected to alter splicing [alternate mRNA splicing was not observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.4186-10G>T (exon 12) strengthens both the natural acceptor ($R_i = 3.1$ -> 5.4 bits; $R_{i,total} = 10.0$ -> 12.3 bits) and a cryptic acceptor site 3nt away ($R_i = 2.1$ -> 4.4 bits; $R_{i,total} = 8.9$ -> 11.2 bits). The wildtype exon would be expected to be the dominant splice form [aberrant splicing was not observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.4674A>G (exon 14) weakens the natural donor ($R_i = 4.9$ -> 2.4 bits; $R_{i,total} = 16.2$ -> 13.7 bits), while a pre-existing 2.8 bit donor is observed ($R_i = 2.8$ bits; $R_{i,total} = 13.9$ bits) 11nt upstream [use of this cryptic donor is observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.4675+3A>T (exon 14) abolishes the natural donor in the same exon ($R_i = 4.9$ -> 0.4 bits; $R_{i,total} = 16.2$ -> 11.7 bits), while the aforementioned 2.8 bit cryptic donor 11nt upstream is unaffected [both exon skipping and cryptic donor use is observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.4986+1G>C (exon 15) abolishes the natural donor ($R_i = 3.6$ -> -15.1 bits; $R_{i,total} = 8.4$ -> -10.3 bits). The most likely cryptic donor site used is 95nt upstream ($R_i = 3.8$ bits; $R_{i,total} = 10.5$ bits), while a similarly strengthened cryptic donor is 65nt downstream with R_i of 4.0 bits ($R_{i,total} = 6.4$ bits) [the latter cryptic site is observed to be activated]
- *BRCA1*:c.5152+2dup (exon 17) abolishes the natural donor ($R_i = 4.4$ -> -5.5 bits), which decreases the strength of the exon ($R_{i,total} = 13.5$ -> 4.0 bits) and could lead to an increase to exon 17 skipping [skipping was observed]
- *BRCA1*:c.5278-22C>G (exon 20) slightly reduces the strength of the natural acceptor ($R_i = 14.8$ -> 14.0 bits; $R_{i,total} = 23.3$ -> 22.5 bits) and is not expected to significantly alter splicing [aberrant splicing was not observed experimentally]
- *BRCA1*:c.5468-1G>A (exon 23) abolishes the acceptor of the terminal exon ($R_i = 9.2$ -> -1.7 bits; $R_{i,total} = 6.9$ -> -4.0 bits). As no nearby cryptic acceptors would lead to an $R_{i,total} > 0$ bits, loss of exon 23 was predicted. A cryptic acceptor 11nt downstream was observed but not quantified, as the site is extremely weak ($R_i = -2.1$ bits; +0.9 bits using an earlier information weight matrix based on ~1800 sites (<PMID: 9711873>)) [authors note that loss of exon 23 cannot be observed]
- *BRCA2*:c.517G>C (exon 5) weakens the natural acceptor ($R_i = 12.7$ -> 10.9 bits; $R_{i,total} = 17.4$ -> 15.6 bits). With no cryptic acceptor of strength comparable to the weakened natural site, only increased exon skipping is predicted [incomplete exon skipping is observed]

- *BRCA2*:c.3326C>T (exon 11) creates a 4.5 bit cryptic donor 3517nt upstream from natural donor (leading to 1416nt long exon), however the $R_{i,total}$ (-2.6 -> 4.5 bits) is less than the natural exon ($R_{i,total}$ = 6.0 bits) and, if observed, is predicted to be the minor splice form compared to the naturally spliced isoform [no change in mRNA splicing observed]
- *BRCA2*:c.4899C>G (exon 11) creates a cryptic donor site (R_i = 1.7 -> 5.6 bits) 1947nt upstream from natural donor (resulting exon is 2986nt long; $R_{i,total}$: 0.1 -> 4.0 bits). Since the strength of the natural exon, $R_{i,total}$, is 6.0 bits, we predict the cryptic splice form to be a minor species relative to wild type [no changes in mRNA splicing observed]
- *BRCA2*:c.6313A>G (exon 11) was not predicted to alter any natural or cryptic donor or acceptor site [no changes in mRNA splicing observed]
- *BRCA2*:c.6841+1G>C (exon 11) abolishes the natural donor (R_i = 7.7 -> -11.0 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 6.1 -> -12.6 bits). Exon skipping is predicted and observed. Two cryptic sites were experimentally observed [leading to exons of size 489nt and 1641nt], of which the former was more likely to be observed (R_i = 6.4 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 8.1 bits). The 1641nt exon is not expected to be as abundant (R_i = 3.2 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 1.9 bits)
- *BRCA2*:c.7618-6G>T (exon 16) strengthens the natural acceptor (R_i = 6.9 -> 10.1 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 6.6 -> 9.8 bits), and no change in splicing is predicted, which was observed
- *BRCA2*:c.8488-9T>G (exon 20) has no effect on the natural acceptor ($R_{i,total}$ = 4.6 bits), but creates a weak cryptic acceptor (R_i = -6.5 -> 1.3 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = -1.0 -> 6.8 bits) 8nt upstream. Cryptic splicing leading to an insertion of 8nt from intron 19 is observed
- *BRCA2*:c.8488-12A>G (exon 20) has no effect on the strength of the natural acceptor, nor does it create a cryptic site and no changes in mRNA splicing are detected
- *BRCA2*:c.8488-14A>G (exon 20) does not affect the natural acceptor ($R_{i,total}$ = 4.6 bits), but creates a cryptic acceptor site (R_i = -8.1 -> 2.8 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = -2.4 -> 8.5 bits) 13nt upstream which is predicted to be used [cryptic splicing causing an insertion of 13nt is observed]
- *BRCA2*:c.8954-5A>G (exon 23) slightly decreases the strength of the natural acceptor (R_i = 7.8 -> 7.2 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 8.1 -> 7.5 bits), while simultaneously creating a strong cryptic acceptor (R_i = 0.7 -> 11.6 bits; $R_{i,total}$ = 0.5 -> 11.4 bits) 4nt upstream of the natural site [the novel cryptic isoform is observed]
- The *BRCA2* mutation that creates a complex re-arrangement of exon 11 ('c.425+415_4780dup[insGATCGAGTGA]') is described to create 4 separate splice isoforms that were detected by RT-PCR (Figure 5). We predict each of these cryptic exons, in contrast with Alamut ($R_{i,total}$ of exon 11 = 6.0 bits): **(1)** Figure 5B describes a splice form which includes 2870nt of exon 11, then 11nt insertion, followed by 293nt of intron 4. This exon would use the natural 9.3 bit acceptor of exon 11, and a 3.6 bit cryptic donor which would result in a cryptic exon with an $R_{i,total}$ of 2.0 bits; **(2)** Figure 5C describes a splice form which includes 1641nt of exon 11 (ending at c.3550) which uses the natural 9.3 bit acceptor of exon 11 and a 3.5 bit cryptic donor ($R_{i,total}$ = 1.9 bits); **(3)** Figure 5D describes a splice form which includes 489nt of exon 11 (ending at c.2398) which uses the natural 9.3 bit acceptor of exon 11, and a 6.4 bit cryptic donor ($R_{i,total}$ = 8.1 bits); **(4)** The fourth isoform (Figure 5E) describes a splice form which entirely skips exon 11, and thus does not include a cryptic donor. The natural donor of exon 10 is 4.1 bits; **(5)** The

complex duplication also creates a novel cryptic donor ($R_i = 4.9$ bits) which overlaps the junction of the 11nt insertion and the intron 4 inclusion, and if used, would lead to a 2882nt long exon ($R_{i,\text{total}} = 3.3$ bits). However, the article does not describe observing this predicted splice form. This situation is not uncommon. We have previously described novel splice site created by a large rearrangement (<PMID: 16319817>).

Disclosure: Information analysis was performed with our commercial software product (www.mutationforecaster.com).